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**A CSR ORIENTED EQUILIBRIUM CAMPUS
PLACEMENT APPROACH****Varun Shenoy* & P. S. Aithal****

Srinivas College of Management and Commerce*, Srinivas University**

City Campus Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575001

E-mail : varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

Abstract

It is a common phenomenon in placements, that a recruiter cannot visit all the institutions in the country or area simultaneously at once for their hiring requirements. Therefore, recruiters agree in a pooling agreement with a host college in the locality for mobilizing the candidates. However, such an arrangement still deems to open up the probability of certain students not reaching the host venue college owing to academic commitments or even personal issues or any other unknown arisable external / internal factors. Considering few recruiters also choosing only one Premium College for hiring owing to their own defined institutional benchmarks and also other unknown relationship criteria again opens up the probability of deprivation of job opportunity for other college students of the nation or a locality for the job positions. Therefore, to create parity in the unequal occurrence of generation of placement opportunity among various educational institutions of the country, in this paper, we recommend a possible equilibrium strategy through researching applications of technology as a cure to this predicament.

Keywords : Universal Campus Placements, Ubiquitous Campus Recruitments, Uniform Placement Opportunity, General Placement Event.

1. Introduction :

This paper primarily focused on Industries is an investigative study as to what solution can be offered to the HEI (Higher Education Institution) students of India when it comes to equal employment placements at their college campuses. There is already fee discrimination in various Government, Aided, Affiliate, Constituent and Private colleges and HEI's across India. Also, in the case of placement process of any of above HEI's, the recruiters or employers are the ultimate main decision makers no matter irrespective how much invitation communication that particular HEI's Placement cell extends to the recruiting companies. However, with an intention to create at-least equality in placement opportunities after all for all students irrespective of colleges and institutions, the job creating and offering recruiter's whole hearted support is sought here to see if the proposed model of placement equilibrium here in this study can be embraced and implemented to be a part of ethics and social responsibility of all involved stakeholders. Therefore, in this study we have offered to propose here a new CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Model. A CSR Programme can be an aid to recruitment and retention, particularly within the competitive graduate student market. Experience reveals most of the organizations take up recruitment and manpower placement as a commercial activity rather

than a social development affair. Therefore, the equal employment placement model proposed here in seeks to align CSR into the placement and recruitment process offered by recruiters of this country to infuse equality into the same.

2. Objectives of the Study :

The broad objectives of this research can be classified as below :

- (a) To create equal placement opportunity for the students of all eligible campuses in the country.
- (b) To develop a sustainable model of provision of equal employment opportunity for all job seeking students of all eligible campuses.
- (c) To facilitate increased healthy Industry-Academia Engagement.

3. Research Methodology :

Based on observations and direct interviews of few focus group of job seeking students, literature review, and secondary data gathering, the research problem i.e. plights of students not getting equal placement opportunities at different Indian HEI (Higher Educational Institutions) was determined. Therefore, the solution model is proposed through a schematic modular representation of ideas and elucidation. An Opinionnaire was also formulated to seek and understand the views from the recruiter sample of a random industry population regarding the model and interpret the results.

4. Proposed new CSR oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Approach :

The Figure 1 below depicts the proposed framework as to how recruiters can offer placement opportunity in their organizations to placement seeking students in HEI's (Higher Educational Institutions) equally. The Funnel down approach proposed here begins from following processes :

- (a) With the help of technology, organize an online application and registration process for all colleges Nationally/State/Region/Area wise depending on company's Manpower requirement location and HEI's surrounding the same.
- (b) The Screening of CV could be done through AI or Bot and issue online interview call letter via mail/test sms or whatsapp to qualified students.
- (c) Organize an Online Proctored employment test for Students which can be taken anywhere so that it saves their travelling time and anxiety.
- (d) Deploy Online Video Conferencing for a Panel GD or even Personal Interviews
- (e) Finally, any other interactions can be done in company facility for shortlisted students.

Figure 1 : CSR Oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Flow

The Primary Significance of the above model is to bridge the time old Industry-Academia gap where both the stakeholders here are in union with their intention of Nation’s Human Resource Development contribution through social service approach. Currently, the divide exists when Academia tries to place their students in the industry through a social contribution approach, the absorbing industry in return is intending to recruit students for commercial or business requirements.

5. Industry Opinion regarding the above Proposed Approach :

The quantified data from Opinionnaire regarding the new model yielded below results from Industry :

Figure 2 : Chart Portraying the Opinoinnaire Results about the Framework

From the above figure, it is found that 47% of recruiters gave favourable approval, 44% of recruiters gave unfavourable approval, 7% of recruiters were neutral on the model, 2% did not solicit any response.

Further Direct Interviews with the sample population revealed that the recruiters who opined unfavourable and neutral conceded that the recruitment process has to be viewed as a commercial activity. Business Pressure as to new unit, expansion or filling vacant positions, client demands make them fill up candidates to meet timely targets overlooking about whether they have time to source the freshers from all colleges. They also opined Government to bring policies on campus recruitment in HEI's. The favourable recruiters however opined they welcome the initiative but needs considerable time to align CSR activities to the domain of HR Recruiting.

6. Conclusion :

The deep divide of Industry – Academia gap here could be widely witnessed projecting its dark effects on career opportunities of less fortunate students of Indian HEI campus left out of placement process due to recruiter's requirements. Therefore, we believe that model proposed in this research could do some justice to the students provided the recruiters embrace it. The Model is proposed keeping all stakeholders involved in mind and also intended to socially satisfy the young HR population of our country through seeking cooperation and support from recruiters.

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